

**English speaking countries and their role in popularization of English as the
language of globalisation**

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Abstract

English is widely used as the official language of the European Union and many Commonwealth countries, as well as many other organizations worldwide. It is the third most spoken language in the world as a first language, after Mandarin and Spanish, according to Ethnologue: Languages of the World. English is also among the official languages of the United Nations – UN. There are six official languages used by the UN English, French, Chinese (Mandarin), Spanish, Arabic and Russian.

Key words: fabulous, immense, amazing, a new world, population, languages, worldwide, among, commonwealth,

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Английский широко используется в качестве официального языка Европейского Союза и многих стран Содружества, а также многих других организаций по всему миру. По данным Ethnologue: Languages of the World, это третий по распространенности язык в мире в качестве первого языка после мандаринского и испанского. Английский также входит в число официальных языков Организации Объединенных Наций – ООН. ООН использует шесть официальных языков: английский, французский, китайский (мандаринский диалект), испанский, арабский и русский.

Ключевые слова: сказочный, необъятный, удивительный, новый мир, население, языки, всемирный, среди, содружество,

The United States, Australia, and England are always the first ones that come to your mind when you talk about English-speaking countries. Undoubtedly, English is the most spoken language (after Mandarin) also; some term it as an international language because no matter where you travel in the world, if you know how to speak and understand it, you are good to go.

Let me share an interesting fact with you: the significant countries I have mentioned at the very start of this blog are not in the list of countries that use English as their official language. However, more than 60 country's official language is English, even though their first language is different. Know that, my dear readers, if you know how to speak English fluently or have a great understanding of reading content in English, then this thing counts as a skill.

Speaking and understanding English in today's world is very important as it opens doors for new opportunities for you. Whether in which area of the world you live in or seeking a job, writing your CV/Resume in English is often considered necessary. Other than this, to develop your own online business or work as a freelancer, you need to command this language as more than 80% of the data you interact with on the internet is in English. So to have access to unlimited opportunities, you have to learn English. Learning English in today's era is a privilege because it is said that if you are lost in the world, you know nothing but the English language, you can easily handle any situation, meet or greet new people, order food in any food café/restaurant and make money.

List of English speaking countries:

After the UK and US, Canada is the third-largest place globally where people speak English fluently, but this doesn't count as their only official language. Other than this, some countries have English as their official language, where more than 13 million speak English (men and women). Together more than 840 million in the world speak English as their first or second language. This shows that knowing English is just like knowing any other skill, and this mastery can make you a strong pillar of any international employment sector.

Below are the tables of top English-speaking countries and countries and their territories that use English as their official language.

Know that these are the countries whose native language is English, but all of them differ in their accent and the usage of certain words. Their style or the way of expressing ideas is what makes them unique. Language is our primary source of communication. It is the method through which we share our ideas and thoughts with others. There are thousands of language in the world. Every country has their own national language in addition to a variety of local languages spoken and understand by their people in

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different regions some languages are spoken by millions of people and others by only a few thousand. In global world the importance of English cannot be denied and ignored since English is the most common language spoken everywhere. English is one of the most used language in the world. Even outside of countries like the USE and the UK, many people can speak and understand English. If you include people who speak it as a second language, an estimated 1 billion people worldwide speak English. On top of this, 67 countries have English as their official language and there are 27 countries that have English as their secondary official language. Throughout the countries the British Empire expanded and ruled over many different countries including most of the ones just mentioned and many more . In many cases ,the British forced the people they ruled over to speak English and some of these countries still speak English ,even if it is not their main language .People often talk about English as a global language . With more than 350 million people around the world speaking English as a first language and more than 430 million speaking it as a second language , there are English speakers in most countries around the world. English may not be the most English is the dominant or official language in a number of countries, including many former British Empire territories. The rise of the British Empire offers many clues as to why the English language is so popular. People often want to know the best language to learn to grt ahead in life .Many think that learning English, the international language, is the best option. English is of course an excellent choice .It is not enough to want to be fluent in English. In order to actually learn English, you have to like learning English. With the help of developing technology, English has been playing a major role in many sectors including medicine, engineering and education, which, in my opinion, is the most important arena where English is needed. If we want a career in travel, English is absolutely essential. As the international language of aviation, pilots and cabin crew all need to speak English. Even if you are not up in the air, speaking English accurately will ensure you are able to communicate with clients and suppliers all over the world. Having a good understanding of communicating in English makes it easier to travel around to globe .Because it is the main international common language for foreigners, knowing English makes it easy to get assistance and in many parts of the world

References

Banerjee, A. and Watson, T.F. (2011) Pickard’s manual of operative dentistry. 9th edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Davidson, A. (2013) ‘The Saudi Marathon Man’, The New Yorker, 16 April. Available at: <http://www.newyorker.com/news/daily-comment/the-saudi-marathon-man> (Accessed: 22 June 2015).

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Guy, J. (2001) *The view across the river: Harriette Colenso and the Zulu struggle against imperialism*. Charlottesville, Virginia: University Press of Virginia.

Hislop, V. (2014) *The sunrise*. Available at <http://www.amazon.co.uk/kindlestore> (Downloaded: 17 June 2015).

Homer (1997) *The Iliad*. Translated by J. Davies. Introduction and notes by D. Wright. London: Dover Publications.

Knapik, J. J., Cosio-Lima, L. M., and Reynolds, K. L. (2015) ‘Efficacy of functional movement screening for predicting injuries in coast guard cadets’, *The Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 29 (5), pp. 1157-1162. EDUC 1028: E-learning. Available at: <http://intranet.bir.ac.uk> (Accessed: 25 June 2015).

Lucas, G. (2004) *The wonders of the Universe*. 2nd edn. Edited by Frederick Jones, James Smith and Tony Bradley. London: Smiths.

Medicine in old age (1985) 2nd edn. London: British Medical Association.

‘Rush (band)’ (2015) Wikipedia. Available at [https://en.wikipedia.org/?title=Rush_\(band\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/?title=Rush_(band)) (Accessed: 18 June 2015).

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